

Ethical Methods and Approaches for Implementing Explainable AI in Healthcare with Relevance to Geriatric Assistive Technologies

A scoping review protocol

Joschka Haltaufderheide ^{1*} and Friederike Speckmann ¹

^{1*}Institute for Ethics and History of Medicine, University Medicine Greifswald, Ellernholzstr. 1-2, Greifswald, 17489, Germany.

*Corresponding author(s). E-mail(s):
joschka.haltaufderheide@med.uni-greifswald.de;

Abstract

Explainability is widely regarded as a key requirement for the ethically responsible use of artificial intelligence (AI) in healthcare. While numerous technical approaches to explainable AI have been proposed, less is known about the ethical guidance, recommendations, and frameworks that inform how explainability should be designed and implemented, particularly in AI-based active and assisted living (AAAL) systems that interact directly with older adults and other care recipients in everyday settings.

This scoping review will systematically map the literature on ethical guidance, recommendations, and frameworks for implementing explainability in AI-based healthcare technologies. The review will follow an adapted Arksey and O'Malley framework and report findings in accordance with PRISMA-ScR. Electronic searches will be conducted in PubMed/MEDLINE, BELIT, CINAHL, Web of Science Core Collection, IEEE Xplore, ACM Digital Library, arXiv, and medRxiv. Eligible publications include empirical, methodological, and conceptual work providing structured guidance on the ethical design or implementation of explainability in healthcare-related AI-systems. Data will be extracted independently by two reviewers and analysed using qualitative framework analysis.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Explainability; Digital health; Healthcare ethics; Active and assisted living; Assistive technologies; Older adults; Scoping review

Introduction

Background

Increasing life expectancy, declining birth rates, and shifts in cultural norms, lifestyles, and societal expectations are significantly altering the global demographic landscape.¹⁻³ By 2050, the proportion of people aged 60 years and older is projected to double from approximately 11% to 22% of the global population.^{2,3}

Population aging is frequently accompanied by a growing prevalence of chronic conditions such as cardiovascular diseases, diabetes, and neurodegenerative disorders.⁴ Dementia, Parkinson's disease, Alzheimer's disease, and related neurodegenerative conditions are among the most significant

contributors to this development.² The increasing burden of such conditions places considerable strain on healthcare systems and challenges existing structures of care. As a consequence, the ongoing demographic transformation requires substantial shifts in healthcare practices and infrastructures. Rather than focusing primarily on the short-term restoration of health, future healthcare systems will increasingly need to support the long-term management of chronic illness, cognitive decline, and age-related functional limitations^{2,4}

In response to these challenges, assistive and enabling technologies⁵ — including services, devices, and infrastructural systems — are increasingly promoted as a means of reducing functional limitations. They may support autonomy, independence, and social participation among older adults while helping to mitigate resource scarcity in healthcare systems.⁶ In particular, advances in digital technologies and artificial intelligence (AI) are emerging as important means in the context of aging and geriatric care.^{7,8} Among other approaches, this includes so-called active and assistive living systems (AAALs): Devices that integrate into care receivers’ daily environments and routines to monitor daily activities, detect health-related behavior and risks, and provide context-sensitive recommendations.^{7–11} By combining sensor technologies, AI-based analytical methods, and natural user interfaces such as chatbots or avatars, AAAL-systems aim to provide context-aware, proactive and accessible support tailored to users’ needs.¹² For example, these systems may detect deviations from expected patterns of daily activities, provide feedback based on their understanding of user behavior, generate alerts about potential health risks, recommend behavioral adjustments, or trigger interventions by caregivers.

In the contexts of AAALs, the outputs of AI-driven technologies may directly influence health-related decisions, behavioral guidance, or safety advice. They therefore shape everyday decisions and care practices in significant ways. Despite their promising potentials, this raises important ethical concerns regarding user autonomy as well as regarding accountability, trust, and the ability of users to understand, evaluate, and potentially challenge system outputs. This especially applies to opaque systems or components.

In response to similar ethical concerns in other fields, explainability has frequently been proposed as a key requirement for the responsible and ethically acceptable use of such systems.^{13–17} Explainability is a loosely defined term often used interchangeably with related concepts such as interpretability, explicability, transparency, or contestability, with meanings that vary across disciplinary contexts and research domains.^{13,17,18} Broadly speaking, explainability can be understood as a property of an AI-driven system that enables relevant stakeholders to reconstruct or understand why or how the system arrived at a particular output or prediction.¹³ In this sense, explainability can be seen as the inverse of epistemic opacity.^{13,19} Epistemic opacity refers to the limited accessibility of computational processes, which may arise from factors such as technical complexity, proprietary restrictions, or insufficient technical literacy among those interacting with the system.^{13,20,21}

However, from an ethical perspective, adequate explainability does not constitute a uniform property that can be specified independently of context. Scholars have distinguished, for example, between explainability that is an inherent property of an AI model (often referred to as *ad hoc* or *intrinsic* explainability) and explanations generated through auxiliary methods that approximate or analyze the behavior of otherwise opaque models (*post hoc* explainability).^{13,17,18,22} Furthermore, explanations may be characterized as either local or global: local explanations aim to clarify why a system produced a particular output in a specific instance, whereas global explanations attempt to describe the overall functioning or decision logic of the system. These distinctions reflect different strategies for rendering AI-systems understandable, depending on their technical architecture and the available analytical methods, each with its own advantages and disadvantages. More importantly, beyond these technical distinctions, adequate explanations are inherently context-dependent and shaped by normative considerations. The ethical appropriateness of a specific explanation may vary depending on what is deemed worthy of protection as well as on the informational needs and cognitive capacities of the intended recipients of an explanation. Consequently, explainability should not be understood as a fixed technical property of AI-systems. Rather, it is a relational and context-dependent concept shaped by technological possibilities, ethical objectives, and the situational context in which explanations are provided.

While different approaches how to develop or implement explainable AI from an ethical perspective have been discussed in the context of clinical decision support systems and diagnostic AI, comparatively little is known about how explainability can be meaningfully implemented in AI-driven active and assistive technologies designed to support care receivers in their daily lives. AAALs differ from many clinical AI applications in important respects. Rather than primarily supporting clinical professionals in diagnostic or treatment decisions, these systems often interact directly with patients or older adults in everyday environments. Explanations may need to be communicated directly to care recipients, informal caregivers, or other stakeholders who may have limited technical expertise or cognitive capacity. Furthermore, explanations may need to be integrated into ongoing interactions between users and assistive systems, for instance through conversational interfaces, visual feedback, or contextual prompts embedded in everyday environments. Consequently, the situational context in which explanations are delivered and the informational needs of diverse user groups may play a particularly important role. Despite the growing development and deployment of AAALs in healthcare, there is currently limited systematic knowledge regarding specific ethical guidance, recommendations or frameworks on how to implement explainability in these contexts. This includes for example recommendations for procedural steps to develop and implement suitable features, availability and suitability of types of explainability, considerations which ethical values should be supported, or what potential trade-offs are. In particular, it remains unclear how specific informational needs and capabilities of care receivers, including, for example, individuals with cognitive impairments or limited digital literacy can be addressed. A systematic mapping of available guidance, recommendations and frameworks to implement explainability in this domain is therefore necessary to better understand the current state of research and to identify ethical and practical challenges associated with the design of explainable active and assistive AI-systems.

Objectives

Against this background, this scoping review aims to systematically map existing guidance, recommendations and frameworks for developing, designing and implementing explainability approaches used in AI-based technologies in healthcare from an ethical perspective and to assess their characteristics, as well as their potential relevance for active and assisted living systems primarily targeting care receivers. Specifically, the review addresses the following research questions:

1. What ethical guidance, recommendations, or frameworks are available for the design and implementation of explainability in AI-based healthcare technologies, and to what extent are they applicable to active and assisted living systems?
2. What are the procedural characteristics (i.e. proposed steps, workflows or sequences) of these approaches?
3. What and how are types and technical implementations of explainability considered?
4. Which ethical values are intended to be supported by these approaches?
5. What ethical trade-offs are considered or implied?
6. How are contextual factors such as informational needs and capabilities of stakeholder groups included?

To this end, the review gathers existing guidance, recommendations and frameworks for design and implementation of explainability and examines their procedural, technical, contextual, and normative characteristics with a view to their usability in AAALs. In particular, it considers aspects such as procedural proposals to develop and implement explainability, discussions on availability and suitability of types of explanation (e.g., feature attribution, example-based explanations, rule-based explanations, narrative explanations, or conversational explanations), considerations of modality of explanations (e.g., visual, textual, speech-based, or conversational interfaces), as well as value considerations (e.g. specific value foci, balancing of values etc.), values intended to support and normative justifications implied or included and considerations of personalization and context-awareness (e.g. how to address specific informational needs) incorporated into these approaches.

Methods

The review will be conducted following an adapted version of the methodological framework proposed by Arksey and O'Malley which provides a structured approach for mapping key concepts, types and availability of evidence and potential research gaps in emerging fields of study.²³ The review process follows a five-step approach, including (1) identification of the research questions (2) identification of relevant studies (3) study selection, (4) charting and analysis of data and (5) summarizing of results. Where appropriate, methodological refinements proposed in subsequent guidance on scoping review conduct will be considered to enhance transparency, rigor, and reproducibility.

Eligibility Criteria

We define our eligibility criteria using the Population–Concept–Context (PCC) framework. No restrictions will be applied with regard to population. This is because the review focuses on the guidance regarding the development, design or implementation of explainability as interactional feature of AI-based systems rather than on specific clinical or demographic user groups. Restricting the review to studies involving only older adults would risk overlooking approaches in other populations that could be transferable to AAAL contexts. Studies involving any population, including patients, older adults, persons with cognitive impairments, informal caregivers, healthcare professionals, or simulated user scenarios, will therefore be considered eligible, provided they address guidance, recommendations or frameworks to design and implementation of explainability approaches in relevant healthcare-related AI-systems.

The investigated concept emerges from the intersection of two key conceptual domains: artificial intelligence and explainability. In line with definitions commonly employed in healthcare and digital health research, this review adopts a task- and cognition-based understanding of artificial intelligence. AI-systems are defined as machine-based systems designed by humans that are capable of performing tasks in ways that would be considered intelligent if carried out by humans.^{24–26} In pursuit of complex goals, such systems can act in physical or digital environments by perceiving their surroundings, processing structured or unstructured data, reasoning on the basis of this information, and selecting actions aimed at achieving specified objectives.²⁷ This operational capacity typically entails a degree of task-specific autonomy.²⁴

For the purposes of this review, explainability is understood as a characteristic of AI-driven systems that enables relevant stakeholders to understand or reconstruct why or how a particular output, prediction, or recommendation was generated. In this sense, explainability can be conceptualized as the inverse of epistemic opacity, that is, the limited accessibility of computational processes resulting from technical complexity, proprietary constraints, or insufficient technical literacy among users.^{13,20,21} More formally, explainability may be described as the ability of an entity A to provide entity B with an explanation of the resolution Z of an AI-system, where the adequacy of the explanation depends both on the complexity and transparency of the processes generating Z and on the communicative and interpretive capacities of those involved.¹³ Accordingly, explainability is treated in this review not merely as a technical property of AI models but as a relational and context-dependent phenomenon shaped by technological affordances, ethical objectives, and situational factors.

In addition, this review focuses specifically on publications that provide guidance, recommendations, or frameworks concerning the ethical design or implementation of explainability in AI-based systems. These terms are understood broadly to encompass structured approaches intended to inform or support decisions about how explainability should be designed, selected, implemented, adapted, or evaluated in practice. This includes, for example, design principles, procedural models, implementation frameworks, methodological recommendations, best-practice guidance, or normative criteria for choosing or tailoring explainability approaches to particular contexts or stakeholder groups. Studies will be considered eligible if they address the aforementioned conceptual domains by providing guidance, recommendations, or frameworks for the ethical design or implementation of explainability in AI-based systems.

Healthcare as a context is defined broadly as any activity or practice aimed at maintaining or improving health through the prevention, diagnosis, treatment, alleviation, or cure of disease,

injury, or physical and mental impairments. This definition encompasses both professional health-care services and individual practices oriented toward health maintenance or functional support. Again, although this review is motivated by ethical challenges arising with the requirement to explainability in AI-based active and assisted living systems, it deliberately adopts a broader perspective not confining itself to geriatric settings. This broader scope reflects the assumption that many approaches to develop and implement explainability may have emerged in other healthcare contexts, such as clinical decision support or digital health applications, that may nevertheless be applicable to AAAL settings.

The review will include original scholarly contributions that describe, develop, evaluate, compare, or critically analyze guidance, recommendations or frameworks to approaches related to explainable AI healthcare-related contexts. Eligible publications may include empirical studies, methodological papers, system descriptions, technical evaluations, and conceptually oriented analyses that provide substantive insights into design and implementation of explainability approaches irrespective of timeframe of publication. The review will include peer-reviewed journal articles, conference papers, and relevant preprints published in English or German. Editorials, commentaries, opinion pieces, and publications lacking sufficient methodological or conceptual detail on explainability approaches will be excluded.

Information sources and search strategy

A comprehensive literature search will be conducted to identify relevant studies. The search strategy will be developed iteratively through preliminary searches and in consultation with the research team. It will combine free-text keywords related to artificial intelligence, explainability, health-care and ethics. Preliminary searches demonstrated no added value of a dedicated search block for guidance- or framework-related terminology, as these concepts are described inconsistently across the literature and lack standardized indexing. Relevant publications were therefore identified through the broader conceptual search strategy and assessed for eligibility during screening. A sample PubMed/Medline search string is shown in table 1.

Table 1 Example search string.

No.	Search term
1	artificial intelligence[Title/Abstract]
2	machine learning[Title/Abstract]
3	deep learning[Title/Abstract]
4	1 OR 2 OR 3
5	explainable[Title/Abstract]
6	explainability[Title/Abstract]
7	interpretable[Title/Abstract]
8	interpretability[Title/Abstract]
9	explicable[Title/Abstract]
10	explicability[Title/Abstract]
11	XAI[Title/Abstract]
12	contestability[Title/Abstract]
13	5 OR 6 OR 7 OR 8 OR 9 OR 10 OR 11 OR 12
14	health*[Title/Abstract]
15	care[Title/Abstract]
16	medicine[Title/Abstract]
17	14 OR 15 OR 16
18	ethic*
19	moral*
20	normativ*
21	18 OR 19 OR 20
22	4 AND 13 AND 17 AND 21

The following electronic databases will be searched:

- PubMed/MEDLINE
- BELIT

- CINAHL
- Web of Science Core Collection
- IEEE Xplore
- ACM Digital Library
- arXiv
- medRxiv

These databases were selected to ensure interdisciplinary coverage of ethical, medical, nursing, technical, and human–computer interaction research. In order to capture recent and emerging developments in explainable AI, relevant preprint repositories will also be searched, including arXiv and medRxiv. The search strategy will be adapted to the specific syntax and indexing structure of each database. No temporal restrictions will be applied in order to capture both foundational and recent contributions in the rapidly evolving field of explainable AI. To enhance comprehensiveness, backward and forward citation chaining will be conducted for all included studies. In addition, targeted searches of grey literature sources will be performed where relevant to identify methodological contributions that may not be indexed in the selected databases.

Study selection and screening

Study selection will be conducted using Catchii (catchii.com). Duplicates will be removed prior to screening. The selection process follows a two-stage approach in accordance with the predefined eligibility criteria. First, title and abstracts of identified records are screened by both authors independently to identify relevant work. Prior to formal screening a pilot phase will be conducted in which a subset of 50 records will be screened jointly in order to develop a shared understanding of the inclusion and exclusion criteria and to consolidate their operationalizability. Second, full-text screening will be carried out independently by two members of the research team per record for all studies deemed potentially eligible during the initial stage. Reasons for exclusion at the full-text stage will be documented. Any disagreements between reviewers will be resolved through discussion. The study selection process will be documented and reported using a PRISMA flow diagram. Consistent with the objectives of a scoping review, no formal critical appraisal of methodological quality will be conducted.

Extraction and analysis

Data extraction and analysis will be conducted using qualitative data analysis software (MAXQDA). Two members of the research team will independently extract relevant data from all included studies using a standardized data charting form. Extracted information will include bibliographic characteristics (e.g., authors, year of publication, study type, application domain) as well as substantive information relevant to the research questions, including procedural characteristics, characteristics of explainability approaches, their intended ethical functions and value considerations, and considerations related to user needs and capabilities.

A qualitative framework analysis is conducted informed by categories derived from the research questions. Qualitative framework analysis is an approach to qualitative data analysis that is particularly suited to conduct analysis informed by an a priori theoretical framework.^{28,29} It combines deductive and inductive analytic strategies by using an initial coding framework derived from theory while allowing for iterative refinement of categories based on close engagement with the data. The analytic process will involve familiarization with the included material, systematic application of the initial coding framework, indexing and charting of data into a matrix structure, and interpretive comparison across studies and analytical categories.

The preliminary coding framework comprises categories addressing (1) procedural characteristics of the proposed approaches (e.g., stepwise implementation processes or workflows), (2) technical considerations regarding explainability approaches and modalities, (3) ethical values and normative justifications underlying the proposed guidance, (4) ethical trade-offs addressed or implied, and (5) contextual considerations, including stakeholder-specific informational needs and capabilities. With regard to the initial identification and categorization of ethical values the review will rely on authors’ self-identification. Rather than applying an external normative framework, it will,

hence, adopt the conceptualization used in the respective publications. Accordingly, values, principles, or considerations will be treated as ethical where they are explicitly presented or discussed by the authors as part of the ethical rationale underlying their proposed guidance, recommendations, or frameworks. This approach allows the review to map the conceptual landscape of the field without imposing a predefined taxonomy of ethical values. In accordance with the principles of framework analysis, these initial categories will be refined iteratively through close engagement with the included studies, allowing additional themes and subcategories to emerge inductively where appropriate.

Synthesis and preparation of Results

Based on the results of the data analysis, a narrative synthesis will be performed. Reporting will follow the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for scoping reviews (PRISMA-ScR).³⁰

Conclusion

AI-based assistive technologies are increasingly deployed in geriatric care and everyday health management, yet the role and implementation of explainability in these systems remain insufficiently understood. By systematically mapping existing guidance, recommendations and frameworks to the design and implementation of explainability approaches and analyzing their procedural characteristics, technical constraints, ethical functions, trade-offs, and alignment with user needs, this scoping review aims to provide a structured overview of current methodological practices and conceptual framings in the field. The findings are expected to contribute to a better understanding of how explainability can be meaningfully designed and evaluated in AAALs, particularly with regard to diverse user capabilities and care situations. In doing so, the review seeks to inform future interdisciplinary research, support ethically grounded technology development, and identify key gaps for subsequent empirical and conceptual work.

Declarations

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare to have no conflict of interest.

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